

INTEGRATING DIGITAL AUTHENTIC AUDIO-VIDEO MATERIALS TO ENHANCE LISTENING

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the use of digital authentic audio-video materials in teaching listening comprehension skills in foreign language classes. It examines the feasibility of using digital authentic audio-video materials in foreign language classes as a means of accelerating the learning process and maximizing its communicative orientation. A survey was conducted among B2 level students studying foreign language and literature to determine which types of digital authentic audio-video materials they prefer to work with. The participants of the study consisted of thirty seven students' first-year at English and literature course (September-December, 2024) from Samarkhand state foreign language institute and data were collected through observation and a survey questionnaire. The findings show that the digital authentic videos positively is defined listening comprehension skills, fostering deeper cognitive engagement, self-directed learning and the students' greater confidence and motivation.

Listening is the process of perceiving and understanding foreign speech. In communicative methods, listening is considered not only as a means of learning, but also as a special type of speech activity. Through listening, students master the sound of speech, the vocabulary of the language and its grammatical structures. Oral communication is impossible without listening; it helps to master speaking, reading and writing. The purpose of listening as a special type of speech activity is to develop listening skills - the ability to understand the meaning of an oral text, the significance of statements and the ability to form one's own attitude to the information heard. Thus, listening exercises are aimed at developing speech, linguistic, socio-cultural, compensatory and educational-cognitive abilities in the process of mastering a foreign language.

Rost's(1994) point of view, among four language skills; speaking, listening, reading and writing, listening is the most critical for language learning at the beginning stages. Practicing listening before speaking or reading, writing could prepare learners to acquire a second language with a greater efficiency. In fact, listening is the most frequently used language skill in everyday life[2].

According to Hamouda (2013) investigated, in listening comprehension, most learners struggle with the problems such as pronunciation, accent, insufficient vocabulary, speed of speech, lack of concentration, anxiety and poor quality of recording. These major listening comprehension problems were encountered by EFL Saudi learners. Furthermore, from Ferris' perspective, EFL teachers must integrate their teaching content with the real world content and linguistic forms. He meant that teachers change their attitudes to consider the language as abstract and academic exercise[2].

Acquiring communicative competence in a foreign language without being in the country where the language is being studied is a very difficult task. Authentic materials, such as audio and video, are essential for achieving these goals. Authentic materials are usually defined as materials created by native speakers. They create an environment of real language communication, making the process of learning foreign language materials more lively, interesting, challenging, convincing and emotional.

Video is one of the most common sources of authentic media educational information. Videos recorded on film or digital media are used as didactic materials that can be viewed multiple times, with the ability to use stop and pause modes and quickly find the desired passage [4]. Their use increases motivation to learn: videos (films) are very motivating in themselves. The language and plots of the videos are taken directly from the target language culture, which contributes to expanding regional knowledge about the target language country, familiarization with the cultural values of native speakers, and the study of speech phenomena of regional geography.

The use of regional geography video materials allows you to implement an intercultural approach - to perceive a foreign culture from your own perspective and your own culture from the perspective of another. The intercultural approach teaches not only how to behave correctly in certain communicative situations, but also how to build a dialogue between your own culture and the culture of the target language country. Thus, the use of video materials helps to implement the most important requirement of communicative methodology - to present the process of language acquisition as an understanding of a living foreign language culture, individualizing learning and developing students' motivation for speech activity[3].

Audiobooks and podcasts develop listening comprehension skills.

Audiobooks are an effective way to learn. A book read by a professional narrator not only provides an interesting story, but also introduces you to the spoken language and pronunciation of words. Many people think that listening to an audiobook requires a lot of time, but in fact it is faster than reading a paper copy. At the same time, you can listen not only to fiction, but also to a professional voice. Audio and video tapes - we can use audio, video, electronic materials such as audio cassettes or discs, video cassettes, television and radio broadcasts to teach English listening comprehension. A podcast is a broadcast of music and speech based on the principle of a thematic and genre radio station. The word PodCast comes from Ipod (music player) and Broadcast (broadcast). Podcasts are audio programs, series, or blogs that you can download or listen to online. The main difference between podcasts and radio is the ability to choose a genre and topic and listen at any convenient time.

METHODOLOGY

To demonstrate which type of digital authentic audio-video materials are comfortable to use and useful to learn, a case study was conducted in a second-year English language and literature course at Samarkhand state foreign language institute. The study involved 37 participants at the B2 proficiency level.

Duration was from September to December in 2024.

Students who participated in the experimental training were given a questionnaire and situational test tasks based on these resources to determine the level of use of digital resources to improve listening comprehension.

Survey results

In the first question, students were asked to rate 7 types of materials intended for listening on a 10-point scale: news, lectures, conversations, podcasts, songs, interviews, films\shows. When processing the data during the survey, we divided the material into three levels of difficulty: high (10, 9, 8 points), medium (7, 6, 5, 4 points), low (3, 2, 1 point). In this way, you can see the students' answers to the first question of the survey.

Table 1.

Results of listening material types

№	Listening material types	Number of students 37					
		High level of difficulty		Medium level of difficulty		Low level of difficulty	
		student	(%)	student	(%)	student	(%)
1	News reports	31	84%	2	5%	4	11%
2	Lectures\academic Talks	20	54%	9	26%	7	20%
3	Conversations\dialogues	16	44%	17	48%	3	8%
4	Podcasts	16	43%	20	55%	1	2%
5	Songs	26	70%	8	21%	3	9%
6	Interviews	31	84%	2	5%	4	11%
7	Movies\TV shows	29	79%	6	16%	2	5%

The result of the survey was that 84% of the participants cited listening to news and interviews as the most difficult type of listening.

The second question in the survey: Which of the following sources do you use to learn listening comprehension and which ones did you find interesting to learn from? Mark your answers with a (v) sign.

Table 2.

Results of listening resource types

№	Listening resource types	Number of students 37					
		High level of interest		Medium level of interest		Low level of interest	
		Student	(%)	student	(%)	Student	(%)
1	Audiobooks	4	11%	2	5%	31	84%
2	Online lectures and webinars	20	54%	9	26%	8	20%

3	Songs	16	44%	17	48%	3	8%
4	Live radio, online radio	16	43%	20	55%	1	2%
5	Interactive language apps	26	70%	8	21%	3	9%
6	Podcasts	26	70%	8	21%	3	9%
7	Youtube videos (BBC channels, Ted Ed)	33	89%	3	8%	1	3%
8	Films	2	5%	6	16%	29	79%
9	Ted Talks	29	79%	6	16%	2	5%

89% of participants highly rated watching the Youtube video hosting application, because in our opinion, understanding through visual viewing is easier than understanding only through hearing.

В.И.Пацыба classifies the advantages of video materials in language learning as follows:

- creating an artificial foreign language
- the ability to close one of the channels of information intake
- developing the ability to observe, describe, generalize what they see
- focusing students' attention on individual language moments
- lack of template and uniformity of statements[5].

Video can help in promoting the language learners' listening comprehension. The structure of language is in the form of ungrammatical features that are not similar to the written language, which can enhance learners' comprehension as well as entertaining them. The connection between the classroom and real world encourage students to understand the relationship between learning and practicing. Video is widely accepted as more powerful and more comprehensible than other media for second and foreign language students[1].

5. CONCLUSION

The integration of the blended learning approach within digital education significantly contributes to the development of B2-level students' listening comprehension skills. The online and collaborative tasks proved to be enjoyable, which increased their motivation to learn and gave them higher confidence in persisting with the progressively more challenging tasks. We believe that combining the online delivery instructed teaching with our traditional teaching can provide our students with self-efficacy and having a sense of control over the listening process, which is fundamental for effective listening. Future research could explore its long-term effects and adaptability for different EFL proficiency levels.

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